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MEDIA LAW AND SELF-REGULATION IN MONGOLIA: CURRENT TRENDS AND INTERACTIONS

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Abstract

This article presents a comprehensive study of the legal environment of journalism in Mongolia from the perspective of legislation and media self-regulation. During this research, more than 890 active laws of Mongolia were examined, and a content analysis of 115 media-related laws was conducted by the authors. In addition, the authors carried out and analyzed a sociological survey among 110 Mongolian journalists regarding how they approach ethical issues at the editorial level. The article also reviews the editorial ethics codes of 80 Mongolian media outlets. Furthermore, around 480 public complaints received by the Media Council, Mongolia's media self-regulatory organization, between 2015 and 2022 were analyzed.

Keywords: Mongolian journalism, media regulation, media self-regulation, journalism ethics, code of ethics, press freedom, Mongolian democracy.

Introduction

Mongolia's transition to a democratic system in 1992 marked the beginning of a free press, and the adoption of the Freedom of the Press Law in 1998 became an important step in protecting media freedom. Since then, more than 100 laws related to media activities have been adopted, but we believe that trying to regulate all issues in media by law has questionable consequences for freedom of speech and expression. Thus, in this research work, the issues of interaction and current state of media self-regulation and law is discussed.

Internationally, the law covering the activities of journalism is explained by the term "mass media law", and only the laws approved by the legislative body, the regulations and resolutions issued following them are considered. However, the concept of mass media regulation includes law and legal issues in journalism and mass media self-regulation.

The legal system consists of a) international documents, b) the constitution of the country, c) laws and regulations of the sector, d) laws and regulations of other sectors, e) norms of social ethics - self-regulation of the sector. Simply put, law can be defined as a solution to these social problems regulation. But the law is one of those many regulations.

"Media regulation" refers to the process by which a range of specific, often legally binding, tools are applied to media systems and institutions to achieve established policy goals such as pluralism, diversity, competition, and freedom (Oxford University Press, орноо байхгүй). Therefore, it is not only related to media activities. The main issue of media regulation is which relations should be regulated by law, and which relations should be left to social norms and the

information market. There are two main approaches to regulating the media environment around the world. First, as much as possible, all activities are prohibited and regulated by law and regulations (authoritarian regime countries), and the second is that journalism activities are entrusted to the market as much as possible.

The countries leading in terms of press freedom mostly adhere to the second approach, or libertarianism. Libertarians believe that giving people a wider field of freedom produces better results than restricting it (Amarjargal.P, 2020). It is very common in countries with authoritarian regimes to demand the legalization of all activities of journalists and media organizations. However, countries with good press freedom, they try to regulate through a softer approach - industry self-regulation, media literacy, and social norms. Generally, it is necessary to regulate by law if any activity cannot be regulated by normal ethical standards or if there are wrong practices in society.

One of the main issues of media law is the relationship norms between the three subjects: the state, the media, and the public. The government always pursues the right to information through surveillance, while the media and the public fight against it. The public also demands and criticizes the media to serve their well-being. Which of these subjects has a strong or weak influence on social media communication and participation determines the quality, accountability, availability, and effectiveness of the information. Therefore, the law established by the state or parliament is likely to create more advantages for the state, and this is also observed.

There is no need for legal regulation, as long as there is a mature self-regulation of the journalism industry and the industry can be managed. But in

reality, there are still problems that cannot be solved by self-regulation of the industry. If the industry's self-regulation cannot solve these new problems and violations, it will be necessary to regulate them by law. If the industry's self-regulation is effective, realistic, and problem-solving, legal regulations are more flexible and lenient.

Media regulation has the following two main responsibilities.

First, it is responsible for protecting the freedom of the press. One of the legal functions of the media is to exercise and protect the public's right to speech,

expression of opinion, publication, and access to information equally and without discrimination.

Second, it is responsible for regulating (limiting) the negative effects of journalism. Lack of journalism professional standards can cause damage to society by infringing on state and personal secrets, becoming a motive for committing crimes, and affecting the deterioration of social ethics and order. The above two functions should be in a proper relationship, but sometimes they conflict with each other.

Consider the difference between law and self-regulation, two important elements that make up the media legal system.

Table #1. Differences between law and media self-regulation.

	Law	Media self-regulation
Purpose	To impose legal responsibility on the guilty party and to compensate the victim	Conciliation
	Social stability and crime prevention	Protect press freedom and prevent journalists from being held legally responsible
Approach	Justice is combined with punishment	Correcting the errors of the media by upholding the principles of journalism ethics and ensuring the rights of victims
Decision maker	Court, Constitutional Court	Members of the Media Council consisting of researchers and industry experts
Measurer	Legislature-Parliament	Based on public and professional ethical norms, it will be discussed within the industry
Scope	All media operating in that country	Even if you do not join the Media Council by accepting the code of ethics, you will decide what is right and wrong by the common code of ethics.
Serving capacity	Documents with the highest legal capacity	Below the law
Source	The power of the state and legal system is based on influence	It is based on trust of journalism organization, civils and the council
Finance	State	Often independent (donations, funding from donor organizations, projects, membership fees)

According to the above table, media self-regulation is a "soft" method as more flexible, more independent from the government, and the position of experts in the field are importantly heard.

Discussion

Today, Mongolia has its own media legal regulation system and is in its development stage. As of 2023, there are 486 media outlets in Mongolia (Press

Institute of Mongolia, 2023). And 890 laws are in force in Mongolia (legalinfo.mn, n.d.), of which 115 are related to the media.

It was mentioned earlier that the feature of regulation of the media is to limit the state's participation in this sector. Authorities try to control the media through laws. This is reflected in the provisions that restrict the media and basic human rights.

Figure #1. Analysis of mass media-related laws in Mongolia.

If you look at this number of media laws superficially, it may seem comparably equal as 62 are restricted or prohibited, and 53 are supportive of media of those 115 laws. However, when we analyze those laws by each clause, different results came. 83.8 percent of the 62 laws with restrictive clauses (10 on human rights and 42 on mass media) restrict freedom of the press. However, if we unpack the laws with supporting content, 66 percent support the government, 22.6 percent support human rights, and 11.3 percent support the media.

To sum up, analyzing the 112 laws related to the media, laws regulated media roles dominate the legal regulation in Mongolia. It is not uncommon to restrict the media by assigning them roles. However, the provisions that support the freedom of the press in actual meaning are a less percentage. Freedom of the press may be restricted to some extent for the good of society. However, it should be noted that if restriction goes too far, it violates the right of citizens to express their opinions and leads to the reduction of freedom of the press.

Self-regulation of media ethics is a system that adheres to professional ethical norms through the guidelines of editorial and professional organizations in the field and informs this procedure to the public. It means that journalists and media workers should voluntarily participate in the development and editing of ethical guidelines by professional organizations; and those codes that have been discussed together and approved should be kept open to the public and they should report how they adhere to them.

The advantages of media self-regulation are:

1. Strengthens democracy - The policy paper "Importance of media self-regulation in protecting freedom of expression" adopted by UNESCO in 2011 states that "Self regulation preserves independence of the media and protects it from partisan government interference. It could be more efficient as a system of regulation as the media understand their own environment better than government (Puddephatt, 2011). In other words, press self-regulation is an effective model for strengthening democracy and developing civil society.

2. Promotes media freedom - In societies where media is regulated directly by the government or in some form of dependency, citizens lose interest in the journalism and thus distrust it. On the other hand, journalists and media organizations are losing their freedom and business. But self-regulatory mechanisms can prevent these harmful effects of distorting democracy. By promoting and self-regulating professional ethical standards, the quality of journalism improves and freedom of the press is supported by increasing opportunities for independent work.

3. Accessible to the public - If a journalist has harmed a citizen through mass media, they can file a complaint to self-regulation organization and correct the information. In this way, the process of restoring one's dignity and making a complaint has the advantage of saving time and money compared to going to court. In addition, some Media Councils include representatives of the public in their structure, which has the advantage of making the council's activities transparent, fair and accessible to the public. In other words, Media self-regulation is the process by which the media industry voluntarily agrees on professional norms and learns to follow them. This process is open to the public. In this way, media organizations demonstrate their ability to work at a professional level and openly accept their responsibilities to the public.

4. Evidence of media responsibility - Mass medias that support the Media Council and adhere to its code of conduct, or acknowledge and correct professional misconduct in accordance with the Council's decisions, are perceived by their recipients as responsible or trying to be responsible media. In this way, public trust in journalism increases.

Journalism ethics self-regulation can be classified into the following three levels and our studies are described under each related level.

1. **The level of the individual journalist:** In most cases, individual journalists and media workers are the main players who make ethical decisions in the practice of journalism. How ethical a decision he makes will be related to the knowledge and understanding of professional ethics as well as the upbringing of the journalist. Also, the culture and norms of the media

organization where he works is another factor that affects ethical decisions.

2. Editorial level: Organizations and communities are one of the most influential subjects in shaping the moral behavior of individuals. Therefore, the ethical self-regulation of editorial level has an important effect not only on the team but also on the moral development of individual journalists. Media organizations are one of the most important implementers of self-regulation. This is because self-regulation of the industry carries out activities aimed at improving the general public and the ethics of the industry, while only the editorial office can organize the work of cultivating journalists, who are the cells of the journalism industry. In other words, the quality of a journalist's work depends on how well the editorial office adheres to ethical principles and how much it pays attention to ethical issues.

At the editorial level, how the mass media pay attention to professional ethics was studied firstly, questioned from 110 journalists, and secondly, by analyzing the ethical codes of 80 popular mass media organizations of Mongolia.

The key results of survey from 110 journalists, which purposed to determine how Mongolian mass medias pay attention to journalism ethical issues and how they manage their experience show that:

× 62.8% of new hires do not receive complete information and introductions about their organization's code of ethics,

× 30% of the participants do not know whether the media organization they work for has a code of ethics,
 × 40.9% did not fully familiarize themselves with the code of ethics even during their working life.
 × 73.6% of editors do not update their code and have not updated it for a long time,
 × 23.7% answered that they do not use their code to make ethical decisions.

The basis of self-regulation of journalism ethics is a code of professional ethics. Principles of professional ethics are defined as “guidelines and recommendations that summarize the basic concepts of professional ethics, are aimed at improving professional performance, and require mandatory adherence” (Choisamba Choijoljav, 2004). The code, a systematic set of guidelines for standard moral, is a document that prohibits certain types of behavior that are considered unethical and defines other types of behavior as ethical. We analyzed editorial codes of ethics and collected editorial-level codes to test their quality and evaluated them against specific criteria.

Codes of ethics of 80 mass media organizations, which are well-known, well-established and highly rated publications in Mongolia were collected and analyzed. Among them, 50 are news sites, 15 are televisions, 7 are daily newspapers (1 is local), 4 are radios, 3 are magazines, and 1 is a news agency.

Table #2. Quantification of what code of ethics the newsrooms adhere to.

<i>Channel</i>	<i>Has their own code of ethics</i>	<i>Adheres to Media Council of Mongolia's Code of Ethics</i>	<i>Adheres to Code of Ethics of Mongolian Confederation of journalists</i>	<i>It says it has its own code, but it can't be shared</i>	<i>Don't have codes</i>	<i>Total</i>
<i>Website</i>	6	16	2	6	23	53
<i>Television</i>	4	3	1	0	8	16
<i>Newspaper</i>	1	5	0	0	1	7
<i>Radio</i>	0	0	0	0	4	4
<i>Magazine</i>	0	1	0	0	2	3
<i>News agency</i>	1	0	0	0	0	1
<i>Total</i>	12	25	3	6	38	84

× 38 out of 80 mass medias sampled in the study (47.5%) do not follow any code of ethics in their activities.

× 26 of the mass medias (32.5%) did not publicly post their code of ethics or refused to post it. The media's activities gain credibility through public exposure. That's why there is an international standard of publicly posting editorial policies and codes of ethics on their websites. This indicates our media outlets does not understand its importance of publicly informing about their professional ethics standard for audiences to gain trust.

× Of the 36 mass media outlets that responded that they have an editorial code of ethics, 24 follow the code approved by the Media Council of Mongolia, and three follow the code approved by the Mongolian Confederation of Journalists, but which has now been revoked. Only 12 newsrooms have their own code of professional ethics (2 refused to share).

• According to the criterias for editorial-level codes, Mongolian mass medias' codes of ethics are generally prescriptive and lack of explanation and regulation. Also, they do not reflect the specifics of their activities, most of them do not reflect the way to comply with sanctions and principles, and they rarely update their code of ethics regularly due to the development of technology and new areas of journalism.

3. Industry level: As for journalism is vital part of mass communication, public trust for journalism is essential. Ethics self-regulatory bodies operating at the industry level are important in strengthening public trust. It also has an important effect on strengthening and developing democracy by connecting media organizations with the public, resolving complaints, and promoting ethical issues.

In 2015, the very first self-regulation organization, the Media Council of Mongolia (MCM) were established and has been responsible for self-regulation

of ethics at the industry level in our country. MCM received 19 complaints in 2015, 41 in 2016, 67 in 2017, 100 in 2018, 106 in 2019, 52 in 2020, 72 in 2021, and

21 in the first two quarters of 2022; received a total of 478 complaints.

Table #3. In 2015-2021, the number of complaints submitted to the ethics committees of the Media Council of Mongolia. Source: Reports of MCM.

As shown in the above graph, 83% of the complaints received by the Newspaper, Website and Magazine Committee and 17% were submitted to the Radio and Television Committee. Although some complaints are delayed, the complainant withdraws or refuses to discuss the complaint; the majority of complaints are addressed to newspapers, websites, and magazines.

separately, thus the decisions of the ethics committees of the MCM were reviewed individually and the information was compared.

In order to analyze complaints for Media Council of Mongolia, the 2015-2018, 2016-2017, 2018, 2019 and 2020 reports published on the council's website were considered. In some cases, for example, the reports of 2017 and 2021 were not published

Except for the years of the COVID-19, the number of complaints submitted to the MCM has been increasing year by year. On the other hand, 43.52% of the cases where the complaint was returned due to lack of necessary information, the complainant withdrew the application, or the hearing of the complaint was delayed or suspended depending on certain conditions. As a result, the complaint resolution rate of MCM is 56% on average, as can be seen from the table below.

Table #4. Quantitative indicators of the resolution of complaints submitted to MCM.

Year	Total number of complaints	Resolution of all received complaints				The decision made after discussing the complaints			Percentage of complaint resolution
		Returned	Withdrawn	Delayed/Suspended	Discussed	No violation	Report decision not mentioning media outlet	Report decision mentioning media outlet	
2015	19	3		7	9	0	7	2	47%
2016	41	3	9	one	29	1	21	7	70.70%
2017	67	26		2	39	2	1	36	58.20%
2018	100	44	7	two	49	24	4	21	49%
2019	106	22	9	1	74	24	14	36	69.80%
2020	52	23	9	0	22**	10	3	9	42.30%
2021	72	43		1	28	11	7	10	38.80%
2022*	21			1	20	8	11	1	95.23%
Нийт дүн	478				270	80	68	122	56.48%

* First two quarters of 2022, **previously delayed 2 complaints increased amount

Successful approach is seen as reflected in above graph, as the number of media outlets without ethical violations is increasing year by year compared to the total number of complaints submitted to MCM. Another progress is the number of media outlets that have been corrected ethical violations or reported without mentioning their names in MCM Ethics Committee discussion report is increasing every year. However, the number of medias that has been reported

as made ethical violations (except for the first two years) is always higher than the media outlets making corrections, which is a provoking indicator. In other words, the indicator of the recognition of the mistakes made by the mass media outlets is insufficient.

Figure #2. Media channels percents that have committed ethical violations.

When looking at media outlets that have committed ethical violations by channel, news sites have the highest number of ethical violations. 270 of the total 478 complaints (up to June 2022) received by the MCM since its establishment were discussed and 190 ethical violations were detected. 78% of it was reported by news sites. Television followed with 14%, while errors made by newspapers accounted for 6%. On the other hand, there was one ethical violation in radio and magazine, each.

Considering the number of complaints received by MCM, the following logic is determined through the years.

- × 2015 - The most of the complaints are about dis-information and non-verification of information.
- × 2016 - The most of the complaints are about defamation.
- × 2017 - The most of the complaints are about defamation, libel, harassment,
- × 2018 - The most of the complaints are about defamation,
- × 2019 - The most of the complaints are about disseminating dis-information and defamation.
- × 2020 - The most of the complaints are complaints about insensitivity to human rights, accusations on irrelevant issues,
- × 2021 - The most of the complaints are complaints about gender and human rights insensitivity,
- × 2022 - The most of the complaints are complaints about gender insensitivity, invasion of privacy and live streaming.

In the first years, most of complaints were related to gossip, libel, harassment and defamation but in recent years, complaints related to the details of professional ethics, such as respect for human rights, working with gender sensitivity, and live streaming have been received.

The 190 ethical violations discussed by MCM (until June 2022) have been committed totally 322 times, relating on the 30 articles and clauses of the "Mongolian Media Ethics Principles" of MCM.

The most common ethical mistakes made by Mongolian journalists through MCM's Media Ethics Principle clauses:

- × 1.1 Check the accuracy of information and avoid making accidental errors related to fact-check. -25%

- × 1.2 Check whether the source is reliable and try to mention it clearly. -15%

- × 1.3 Always keep in mind that headlines, photos, videos, audios, graphics, sound bites and quotations should not misrepresent, oversimplify or highlight incidents out of context. -11%

- × 6.2 Names, photos and other personal information will be made public only for the benefit of the public. -9%

- × 1.8 Fair reporting includes giving the opportunity to persons to comment allegations of third parties. -9%

- × 1. Truly informing the public and maintaining human dignity are supreme values of journalistic media. Verification of information is the basic principle of accuracy. -9%

- × 1.5 Analysis and Commentary should be labeled and not misrepresent fact or context. -3%

- × 5. Plagiarism, malicious misrepresentation, use of information for the personal advantage, slander, libel, deliberate accusations, the acceptance of a bribe in any form in consideration of either publication or suppression of information are unacceptable. -3%

- × 4.2 No one shall be presumed guilty unless proven guilty by the court. -2%

Here it is evident that media outlets do not exercise due diligence, do not know the source or gossip, copy the work of others, do not respect individual rights, impose opinions, insult others and do not provide balance of information.

Conclusion

Laws and self-regulation in the media sector aim to strengthen press freedom and create a strong framework for the public's right to know. However, the above studies show that the media law and self-regulation are not compatible in Mongolia, where free journalism is developing. In other words, in recent years, the journalism industry has been trying to develop through self-regulation, but the legal regulation has become more and more strict, and on the contrary, it can be seen from the research related to the law that it is trying to stifle media freedom.

According to the report of Reporters Without Borders, Mongolia, which was still in the "partly free" category, has fallen 10 places in terms of press freedom in the last 10 years, but it is directly related to cases where legal restrictions prevail, journalists' and press

freedom are attacked, and citizens' rights to express their opinions are violated. This is another indicator of the weak self-regulatory power of the industry and the authorities' attempts to limit press freedom.

In Mongolia, self-regulation of journalism ethics is lost most at the organizational or editorial level. The fact that the editors do not pay attention to the ethical issues of journalism is directly reflected in the fact that only ten out of 486 media outlets have developed their own code of ethics. Research has shown that there are few mass media that have their own code of ethics, journalists do not present their code when they get a job, journalists do not even know if they have a code, they do not update or use their code, and it is not clear how to solve when a journalist gets into a complicated ethical situation.

The establishment of the Media Council of Mongolia in 2015 in order to create self-regulation of ethics in the journalism industry is a major step in shaping a professional and ethical information environment. First, it solves journalism ethical issues based on citizens' complaints and demands, and secondly, it provides professional services to ensure the natural development of media freedom. It is worth mentioning that the Media Council of Mongolia is considered a "lighthouse" of self-regulation of journalism and is becoming a good example in Asia.

Although the self-regulation system, which is the basic norm of journalism to be independent from the government, is developing at the industry level, the legal system is deteriorating more and more. It appears

that the ruling center-left party in Mongolia is interested in restricting the media industry by law if it does not respond seriously. Therefore, if there is an interest in preserving free press in Mongolia, it is important for the journalists, researchers, NGO's and media outlets to respond to the approved laws, oppose their approval, cancel them if they are approved, and not only that, but also provide a strong voice aimed at protecting and supporting the freedom of expression and publication.

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